

22NRM06 ADMIT

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1. Summary

This Good Practice Guide focuses on current generation systems designed for the calibration and testing of equipment under controlled conditions. It addresses the generation of AC and DC currents up to 2 kA, including the capability to superimpose disturbances or frequency components up to 150 kHz on the fundamental waveform.

These generation systems are essential for evaluating the performance of devices such as instrument transformers and medium voltage systems under realistic conditions. The guide outlines best practices to ensure waveform integrity stability when generating high voltage signals with superimposed high-frequency components.

2. Introduction

One of the main objectives of the 22NRM06 ADMIT project [1] is to develop advanced current generation systems capable of producing high-current AC and DC waveforms with superimposed frequency components representative of real-world grid disturbances. These systems are essential for supporting the testing and calibration of equipment operating under complex power quality (PQ) conditions, particularly in the 9 kHz to 150 kHz frequency range. By providing controlled high currents and high-frequency content, the guide enables accurate evaluation of current transformers (CTs) and other current-sensing devices under realistic operating scenarios.

In modern medium-voltage (MV) networks, the proliferation of power electronic converters and switching devices causes significant harmonic disturbances up to the 150 kHz band [2, 3]. To properly test current transformers (CTs) and other current-dependent devices under these conditions, especially those installed in MV grids where such supraharmmonic disturbances are present, it is crucial to generate current waveforms that closely replicate those found in actual power systems. However, facilities capable of generating high currents with controlled, traceable high-frequency components up to 150 kHz are currently very limited. Even among leading national metrology institutes (NMIs), most high-current generation systems are restricted to frequencies below 9 kHz. Recently, the EMPIR 19NRM05PQ extended calibration and measurement capabilities (CMCs) of NMIs involved in the project, which, in the near future, will be able to support the increase of the metrology capacity of EURAMET Member States whose metrology programmes are at an early stage of development [4]. Similarly, commercial high-current amplifier systems often fall short of the performance requirements necessary for precise CT characterization in the supraharmmonic range. As a result, validated and stable current generation systems have become a critical component of the test setup. Realistic AC and DC current waveforms with accurately controlled spectral content up to 150 kHz are indispensable for the evaluation of current-dependent devices.

The ADMIT project aims to bridge this technological gap by developing novel current generation infrastructure. These systems enable the production of AC currents up to 2 kA (rms) and DC currents up to 2 kA, with controlled superimposed components spanning the 9 kHz to 150 kHz range [5]. This development represents a major step forward, empowering NMIs and calibration laboratories to offer new calibration services and extending traceability into a frequency range that is increasingly relevant for modern electrical networks.

This Good Practice Guide provides technical guidance for both metrology institutes and industrial laboratories in implementing and using the advanced current generation systems. It outlines procedures for maintaining signal fidelity, e.g. managing inductive load effects and minimizing coupling between fundamental and high-frequency components, and for calibrating the output to ensure traceability. Ultimately, adoption of the practices in this guide will improve the reliability of instrument transformer calibrations and type tests under non-sinusoidal conditions, supporting the development of more robust MV measurement infrastructure and compliance with emerging PQ standards.

The architecture and implementation of the current generation systems, along with associated design considerations and traceability chains, are detailed in the subsequent sections of this guide. Following this introduction, Section 3 describes various generation techniques used by the different institutes (RISE, VSL and VTT), summarizing current generation capability for simultaneous generation of fundamental and high-frequency current sinusoidal components with two parallel separated generators. Section 4 described a generation technique used by UniCampania and INRIM generating simultaneous generation of fundamental and high-frequency current sinusoidal components with two common grounded parallel generators. Section 5 describes the generation technique used by FFIL, summarizing their current generation

capability for simultaneous generation of fundamental sinusoidal components and high-frequency current transient damped components. Section 6 summarizes the conclusions and recommends best practices for both metrological and industrial applications.

3. Two parallel separated current generation

This section presents three different solutions for generation and measurement systems by RISE, VSL and VTT for calibration of current sensors from 50 Hz to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and from 2 kHz to 150 kHz up to 100 A.

3.1. RISE system

At RISE an AC current generation system has been developed using two current sources suitable for calibration of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from 2 to 20 kHz up to 100 A and 20 A for frequencies up to 150 kHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

3.2. Set-up

A Chroma 61605 is computer controlled in frequency and amplitude via a DA converter, e.g. NI USB 6216, which current is feeding a Nokia step-up transformer. The computer interface can either lock-in to the local power frequency or be run at 50 or 60 Hz with a general mixture of harmonics up to 2 kHz synchronized or free-running via an Agilent 33500B. A HITEC Zero-Flux core is used for measurement of the signals from the line frequency and harmonics thereof. The signal is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the line frequency and harmonics current.

Figure 1. Schematic of the RISE set-up.

The supraharmonics are generated from a computer-controlled Keysight 33500B driving a modified Clarke-Hess 8200 amplifier. In this manner a line frequency/phase and frequency independent current with single frequency or spectrum of supraharmonics is generated from 2 to 150 kHz. From a 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D (RISE model) the voltage is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the supraharmonic current. The computer program gives the fundamental and/or one or several harmonics feeding

the Chroma 61605 generator and a mixture of supraharmonics to the Clarke Hess. The fundamental can be synchronized with the grid line frequency. The set-up is shown in Figure 1.

The components in Figure 1 and 2 and their functions are the following:

- Core controller - LabVIEW program “Follower”: This program generates signals for the testing and **slowly ramps up and down the currents** to avoid overvoltage from inductances or transients. The program also collects the signals from the three CTs via a PXIe-6396 digitizer.
- Digitizer PXIe-6396: The signals from the reference CTs, i.e. a HITEC 500/2000 or 6000A (peak current) measuring the line frequency and harmonics and a current shunt RISE CS2D measures the supraharmonics up to 100 A, are sampled by this digitizer. The digitizer has 8 channels simultaneously sampled, 18 bits resolution and a sampling rate up to 15 MS/s. Supraharmonics are sampled at least with a sampling rate = 2^n , larger than $5 \cdot 150$ kS/s (7 periods), which is $2^{20} = 1.05$ MS/s. This choice is for adaptation to the FFT analysis to avoid spectral leakage. The sampling length is dictated by the line frequency, i.e. a duration of at least 7 periods of 50Hz = 140 ms, rounded to 200 ms, about 200 kS.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (Agilent 33500B): Samples the power line frequency for generation of true voltage and harmonics via a computer controller (LabVIEW “follower”). The 33500B generates the waveshapes for supraharmonics and controls the output of the generator Clarke-Hess 8200.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (NI-USB 6216): Provides a wave shape output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 1 kHz). This signal can be synchronized to the line frequency and can contain harmonics with amplitude and relative phase.
- A Chroma type 61605 4 kVA generator is used to generate currents controlled by the NI-USB 6216 arbitrary wave form generator via an external input from 15 – 1000 Hz with 32A/20A (150V/300V) ranges. Using a step-up transformer 100:1 the maximum current is 3.2 kA.
- A modified transconductance amplifier Clarke-Hess 8200 is used for generation of supraharmonics up to 150 kHz. The amplifier can generate 100 A up to 20 kHz and 20 A up to 150 kHz, limited by the compliance voltage of 7V. The waveshape of the amplifier is controlled by the computer program via an Agilent 33500B.

3.3. Test of the generation system

The two generation systems are tested exciting the fundamental 50 Hz combined with an odd harmonic, e.g. 150 Hz, 250 Hz, ... using the Chroma 61605. This at the same time combined with supraharmonic frequencies excited with the Clarke-Hess 8200 close to 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz and 20 kHz up to 100 A, and 50 kHz, 100 kHz and 150 kHz up to 20 A, while avoiding multiples of the fundamental frequency. The limiting factor for the currents above 20 kHz was the compliance voltage from the inductance in the loop where the Clarke-Hess 8200 can drive up to 7 V.

3.4. Preliminary results

The Current sensor Pearson 301X (Fig. 1) was used to test the system. This sensor can measure up to 400 A and is designed for impulse current measurements. A mixed signal of 50 and 150 Hz, with amplitudes up to 365 A @ 50 Hz and 35 A @ 150 Hz was generated with the Chroma 61605 + transformer and several supraharmonic signals around 20 A from 2 to 150 kHz were injected with the Clarke-Hess 8200. In Figure 2 the ratio error and phase error are plotted. The Pearson 301X is apparently not very good at lower frequencies which was expected from the impulse design. For the supraharmonics it behaves well and is within 0.08% for the ratio and within 3% phase error.

Figure 2. Preliminary results for a Pearson 301X impulse current sensor.

3.5. Measurement uncertainties

The ref CT (HITEC Zero-Flux cores) have errors less than 50 ppm and 60 mrad at 50 Hz, and 200 ppm and 1 rad at 1 kHz. Using corrections the phase displacement can be reduced for the Zero-flux cores. The high frequency reference the current shunt RISE CS2D, has an uncertainty of less than 2 ppm for the amplitude from 50 Hz to 150 kHz, less than 2 μ rad at 50 Hz and up to 200 μ rad around 25 kHz for the phase using a linear correction. Calibration of amplitude error and phase shifts of both sensors and using corrections can be used to improve the performance.

The PXIe-6396 has a specified measurement uncertainty of <200 ppm for the amplitude. After calibration we expect this to be better than 100 ppm. The phase uncertainty depends on the sampling frequency and delays between the channels. The digitizer has a simultaneous sampling of all channels, so this reduces delay contributions to the phase uncertainty. The specified timing accuracy is 50 ppm of sample rate, which means the higher sampling rate the lower is this contribution. Further description of the measurement system and a detailed analysis of the measurement results will be published in a paper.

3.6. VSL system

At VSL an AC current generation system has been developed with the aim of generating 2 kA at the fundamental frequency and at least 20 A from 9 kHz up to 150 kHz. This generation system is meant to characterize window-type current transformers, where it can be used to feed the separate parallel power frequency and high frequency branches.

Current transformers can be characterized using bridge or comparator techniques, shunt-based methods, or comparison using sampling methods. In this report, the latter technique is envisaged, in which a high current is simultaneously fed through the primary windings of the CT under test and a reference CT, such that the complex ratio of the secondary currents provides a direct indication for the complex ratio error of the CT under

test (i.e., magnitude error as well as phase displacement). The secondary currents can be measured using step-down transformers, current buffers, and high-precision sampling voltmeters at high accuracy [6], or using a power analyser as a simplified method [7].

Figure 3 shows a schematic overview of the measurement setup for characterising the DUT and reference CT. A high-current source produces the required primary excitation current (I_p) at a single frequency ranging from 50 Hz to 150 kHz via two transformers connected in series. The power analyser's current channels (sampling ammeters) use internal coaxial shunts to monitor secondary currents. The setup's current generating circuit includes a compensation capacitor and inductor to prevent DC magnetisation of the CT cores and to provide series compensation for the circuit impedance.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the measurement setup where a high-current source feeds both the DUT CT and the reference CT [2]. The secondary outputs are recorded using a power analyser for ratio comparison.

3.7. High-frequency generation system

The basic idea of the distorted high-current generation system is to generate the 50 Hz fundamental component with current magnitudes up to 2 kA and the high-frequency components separately, i.e., the fundamental component and the distortion are generated through two separate systems and carried through two separate conductors. The two conductors can be sensed simultaneously by the CTs when feeding them both through the primary winding of the CTs. The generation and measurement of the fundamental component has been well described in literature. Therefore, the focus of this report is on the generation of the high-frequency distortions.

To generate the required high-frequency distortions of 20 A in the frequency range of 50 Hz to 150 kHz, a high-bandwidth power amplifier system was constructed, as illustrated in Figure 4. This system is designed to maintain stable, safe, and accurate current injection into the primary circuit under varying frequency-dependent load conditions. Because of the DUT and reference CT system are simultaneously measured, a small deviation/drift of a couple of percent deviation from the ideal current is not an issue.

Figure 4. High-bandwidth power amplifier system for generation of currents up to 150 kHz.

The components shown in Figure 4 and their functions are as follows:

- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG): Provides a sinusoidal voltage output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 150 kHz).
- Variable Potentiometer (POT): Allows gradual adjustment of the input voltage to the power amplifier. As the impedance of the primary circuit changes with frequency, the potentiometer is used to fine-tune the output and achieve the target 20 A current, as verified by the clamp meter. This allows for a gradual and safe ramp-up of the primary current.
- Amplifier (AMP): Converts the AWG voltage into a current signal. This broadband power amplifier (Hero-Power DCU 2250-10 FM 1295 by Rohrer Mess- & Systemtechnik) provides sufficient gain and power to overcome the inductive and capacitive reactance of the primary circuit at high frequencies.
- Inductor (L): Connected in parallel with the CTs to divert any DC components originating from the amplifier. This is to prevent core magnetisation in the CTs, which could lead to measurement errors.
- Compensation Capacitor (C): Placed in series with the CTs, this capacitor helps to block DC and further ensures that only AC current is present in the measurement circuit. It also helps with series compensation of the long cable connected that loops through the CTs.
- Current Clamp (Clamp): Provides a convenient means for real-time monitoring and adjustment of the primary current during ramp-up and operation. Accurate measurement of the primary current is done using the sampling ammeter, not the current clamp.

3.8. Testing of the generation system

To ensure standardized and consistent characterization, the generation system delivers a primary current up to 20 A to the CTs under test. The primary current is tested at a series of discrete frequencies: 50 Hz, 100 Hz, 200 Hz, 500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz, 20 kHz, 50 kHz, 75 kHz, 100 kHz, 125 kHz, and 150 kHz (a total of 14 points). These frequency points were selected to provide approximately three measurement samples per decade (with some extra points at higher frequencies, as this is most the most interesting). Magnitudes higher than 20 A were generated for frequencies up to 100 kHz. For higher frequencies, the power amplifier could no longer provide sufficient power. The highest magnitude obtained at 150 kHz was still 14 A, however. These currents were measured using a Yokogawa WT5000 broadband power analyser (with 1 MHz bandwidth).

The primary current generation system was further tested by measuring the primary and secondary currents of two similar NRC electronically compensated current transformers [8], with an accuracy of about 1 ppm at 50 Hz and a nominal turns ratio of 100:1. Figure 5 shows the measured ratio between the primary and secondary currents for the two CTs investigated in this study. The magnitude of the current applied was 10 A over the whole frequency range. The primary and secondary currents were measured using 30 A and 5 A input modules of the WT5000 with proper range selection, respectively.

Figure 5. Primary-to-secondary current ratios for the two CTs A and B. Deviations become more pronounced above 10 kHz.

The CTs use internal compensation electronics to ensure low errors (less than 20 ppm and 20 μ rad) up to 5 kHz. However, the internal amplifiers' bandwidth, in particular, restricts the effectiveness of correction beyond a few kilohertz; subtle differences in electronics between the two CTs could have an impact on high-frequency performance. This explains the differences between CT A and CT B observed in Figure 5. A further description of the measurement system and a detailed analysis of the measurement results, including an uncertainty budget, can be found in [2] and will be left for a separate report.

3.9. VTT system

3.10. Low-current multitone harmonics system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is shown in Figure 6. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the transconductance amplifier (Guildline 7620), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos WFD20). A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC. A typical recorded reference multitone signal and its FTT are shown in Figure 7.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage.

Figure 7 shows an example of a recorded frequency response of a wideband current sensor (Pearson 110A) between 50 Hz and 150 Hz.

Figure 6. VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

Figure 7. An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC. As the sampling is coherent with the multitone excitation signal, no windowing is needed for each generated harmonic to fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage. Figure 7 shows an example the measured multitone signal and its FTT.

3.11. High-current low frequency system

This multitone current generation system can be used together with VTT high-current system for power frequency calibration. The high-current generator has a bandwidth up to 1 kHz, and it can generate up to 8 kA at 50 Hz. This system can be used together with the multitone system for calibration of supraharmonics of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 Hz or 60 Hz up to 8 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from DC to 100 kHz up to 20 A and 2 A for frequencies up to 1 MHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

4. Two parallel-grounded generators

4.1. Proposed generation architecture by UniCampania and INRIM

The proposed general generation architecture is shown in Figure 8. It is based on the use of two different current sources: one is dedicated to the generation of Low Frequency (LF) DC or AC 50/60 Hz current with high-amplitude ($i_{LF}(t)$) while the other source is used to generate low-amplitude currents with frequencies up to several hundreds of hertz ($i_{HF}(t)$). Two blocking elements are connected in series with the current generators when it is necessary to protect each generator from the current generated by the other one. Downstream of the filtering elements, the two currents are provided to the measurement branch which consists of the device under test (DUT) connected in series with the reference transducer (REF).

The scheme in Figure 8 is flexible and can be easily adopted in several cases and some of them are here recalled. Regarding the generation of the high amplitude currents $i_{LF}(t)$, two cases can be distinguished: DC currents and AC 50/60 Hz currents. For the DC case, high current levels can be obtained using a commercial generator, a transconductance amplifier or a generation system composed by a three-phase generator coupled with an autotransformer and a rectifier.

Figure 8. General scheme for the characterization of MV/HV current sensors under a current signal composed of high current at DC/power frequency with low amplitude and high frequency superimposed tones

For the AC 50/60 Hz high current generation, the common adopted solutions are power transformers, commercial amplifier, power generator coupled with step up current transformers (CTs).

For the generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ it is possible to use step up current transformers for MV application up to ~100 A suitably designed to have a flat frequency response within the desired band or a commercial transconductance amplifier.

Depending on the adopted solution, it can be necessary to appropriately design the blocking element. The input quantities in the design process are the current levels and their frequency content, the input impedances of the two current generators and the impedance value of the series connection of the device under test and the reference one.

4.2. Experimental setup and procedure

This Section introduces the experimental setup and the test procedure applied to assess the validity of the proposed architecture. The primary objective of the experimental activity presented here is to quantify the mutual impact between the two sources and the resulting current flowing into the measurement branch. In other words, the tests aim to evaluate how the presence of the LF generator affects the HF current in the measurement branch, and vice versa.

Starting from the general scheme presented in Section III, two cases are implemented:

- in the first case (case A), both $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$ are generated using two transconductance amplifiers, each driven by an Arbitrary Waveforms Generator (AWG).
- in the second case (case B), the $i_{LF}(t)$ current is generated using a power amplifier coupled with a step-up CT whereas the $i_{HF}(t)$ is obtained by using a transconductance amplifier coupled with an AWG.

4.3. Generation and Measurement Setup

Considering Case A, the transconductance amplifiers used are one Clarke Hess 8100 and one Clarke Hess 8200. The two transconductances are driven by two Keysight 33500 B AWGs (± 10 V, 120 MHz, THD lower than $300 \mu V/V$). Despite the dual-channel capability of the AWG, two separate AWGs are used to mitigate potential errors stemming from crosstalk phenomena among the channels.

For Case B, the HF tones are generated using a Clarke Hess 8200 driven by a Keysight 33500 B. As for the LF fundamental component, two different step-up current transformers with different features have been used:

- CT1: for MV application, 5/75 A/A, series inductance L_s of $19 \mu H$.
- CT2: window type, 5/250 A/A, series inductance L_s of $0.5 \mu H$.

Both in Case A and Case B, the generated current flowing into the measurement branch is measured by the means of a reference shunt Fluke A40B (flat frequency response within tens of ppm up to 100 kHz) and a Fluke 8588 A multimeter used in digitizer mode with a sampling frequency of 2 MHz.

4.4. Test Procedure

As already mentioned, the main goal of the performed experimental activity is to quantify how each source affects the current in the measurement branch generated from the other source when they are both active. To this end, the test procedure involves three steps:

1. the sole generation of $i_{LF}(t)$,
2. the sole generation of $i_{HF}(t)$ and
3. the simultaneous generation of the two currents $i_{LF}(t)$ and $i_{HF}(t)$.

The first two steps are indicated in the follow using the subscript "S" whereas for the third step the subscript "FHF" is used indicating that the resulting current is composed by a fundamental tone plus a high frequency component.

Experimental results are presented as the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ associated with the current tone at frequency f , measured during the FHF test, compared to those measured during the single tone test S. Mathematically, the errors $\varepsilon(f)$ are defined according to Equation 1:

$$\varepsilon(f) = \frac{I_{FHF}(f) - I_S(f)}{I_n(f)} \quad (1)$$

where I_{FSH} and I_S are the RMS values of the current at frequency f measured under FHF and S test, respectively; I_n is the nominal RMS value of the current at frequency f . Since the only difference between the single-generation test S and the FHF test is the presence of both the generators, the index $\varepsilon(f)$ quantifies the impact on the current tone at frequency f flowing into the measurement branch due to the presence of a second generator producing a current at different frequency and amplitude.

As regards the test points of the preliminary experimental activity here presented, the LF fundamental component is fixed at 50 Hz whereas the HF tone frequency ranges from 10 kHz to 150 kHz with amplitude equal to 10 % of the LF tone.

4.5. Experimental results

In the following, the results of the two investigated configurations are discussed.

4.6. Connection of two transconductance amplifiers

Initially, steps 1 and 2 for exclusively generating one of the two currents are performed by setting the other generator in three different modes: 1) in standby and not connected to the circuit (galvanic insulation), 2) in standby but connected to the circuit (standby), 3) generating 0 A and connected to the circuit (operate 0 A). Considering the case of the solely generation of $i_{HF}(t)$, results related to these three configurations of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator are provided in Fig 9. By the comparison of the curve obtained in standby mode and the one measured with galvanic insulation, it can be observed that deviations go from 170 μA at 10 kHz to 1.5 mA at 150 kHz. Considering the case of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator connected to the circuit and producing 0 A and the case of galvanic insulation of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator, higher deviations are observed with the increase of the frequency. Specifically, at 10 kHz deviation is lower than 200 μA but it increases to 180 mA at 150 kHz.

Figure 9. $i_{HF}(f)$ values measured under three configurations of $i_{LF}(t)$ generator: connected to the circuit and generating 0 A (blue line circle maker), connected to the circuit but set in standby mode (red line square marker) and disconnected from the circuit (yellow line asterisk marker).

The main result of this preliminary experiment consists in the verification that the transconductance amplifier exhibits different impedances and behaviours, depending on its configuration. The results shown in the following refer to the case in which the single test S is conducted by galvanically isolating the other generator.

Figure 10. Errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the iLF(t) generator is connected to the circuit and generating 40 A at 50 Hz, compared to the case when the iLF(t) generator is galvanically isolated.

Focusing on the comparison between FHF and S test, Fig. 8 provides the values of the errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated to the HF tones whereas for the 50 Hz current, the maximum error $\epsilon(50 \text{ Hz})$ is 50 $\mu\text{A/A}$.

Looking at Fig. 10, it can be observed that the presence of iLF(t) generator has a low impact on the iHF(t) flowing into the measurement branch up to 50 kHz being the error $\epsilon(f)$ lower than 0.3 %. The 1 % threshold is reached at ~ 80 kHz whereas at 150 kHz the error increases to 4.50 %. As a general consideration, it can be observed that the error curve has a positive polarity for all the frequencies that, according to Equation 1, turns into higher values of HF currents in FHF test with respect to the HF current measured under single test S case.

To better investigate this phenomenon, the same test procedure is performed by selecting two different gains of the transconductance amplifier used to generate the 50 Hz iLF(t) current at 40 A: 10 S and 100 S. The comparison of the obtained results is provided in Table 1 where it can be observed that for 100 S gain case, error five times higher is measured at 150 kHz. The results of these experimental tests underscore that under the FHF test there is a coupling between the two generators that leads the LF generator to capture, amplify and generate HF components too.

However, between the two cases 10 S and 100 S, an increase in error by a factor of 10 is not observed even if the gain increases ten times because the change in the transconductance gain also results in a modification of its output impedance.

In summary, the generation setup composed by two transconductance amplifiers poses no significant issues for the generation of the iLF(t) at 50 Hz with superimposed HF tones up to 80 kHz, with errors lower than 1 %. However, when frequencies increase from 80 kHz to 150 kHz, the coupling between the generators leads to a rise in the error $\epsilon(f)$ of up to 4.5 %.

Table 1. Impact of the gain of the transconductance used to generate 50 Hz current on the HF tones

Frequency (kHz)	ε (%)	
	10 S	100 S
10	0.000	-0.042
20	0.042	0.022
50	0.278	0.493
100	1.347	3.053
125	2.468	7.130
150	4.496	21.141

4.7. Connection of a step-up current transformer and a transconductance amplifier

As said in Section IV, this configuration is setup with two different CTs. For both, experimental results are presented in Fig. 11 for the HF tones; instead, errors lower than 500 $\mu\text{A/A}$ are measured at 50 Hz. As it can be observed, the different specifications of the two CTs result in errors $\varepsilon(f)$ that differ significantly, by an order of magnitude. For CT1 $\varepsilon(f)$ is always lower than -1 % whereas for CT2 goes from -9.7 % at 10 kHz to -5.7 % at 150 kHz.

However, in both cases the errors are always negative, which means that $I_S(f) > I_{HF}(f)$. Therefore, the connection of the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator to the circuit causes part of the $i_{HF}(t)$ current to flow through the $i_{LF}(t)$ generator instead of the measurement branch.

This phenomenon is inversely proportional to the current frequency because, as the frequency increases, the output impedance of the step-up transformer, which can be approximated as $Z=j\omega L_s$, also increases.

Based on this consideration, it is clear why the errors in HF current tones are much lower when CT1 is used as a step-up transformer for generating 50 Hz current with respect to CT2. In fact, L_s of CT1 has a value about 38 time higher than the one of CT2.

Additionally, CT1 has a significantly lower turns ratio than CT2, with the two being in a ratio of $\sim 1:15$. The turns ratio t is a crucial parameter because the output resistance and inductance of the power amplifier used to drive the CTs, are reflected to the CT secondary side with a factor equal to $1/t^2$. Therefore, since the same power amplifier is used in both cases, the impedance of the amplifier is reflected to the secondary side of CT1 weighted by $(5/75)^2$, while for CT2 it is weighted by $(5/250)^2$.

Figure 11. Errors $\epsilon(f)$ associated with HF tones measured when the iLF(t) generator composed by power amplifier and CT1 (blue line circle marker) and CT2 (red line asterisk marker) are connected to the circuit and generating the fundamental tone, compared to the case when they are galvanically isolated.

To improve the performance of the generation system based on the use of the CT2, it is possible to introduce an inductive blocking element (BlockHF) into the circuit to reduce the $\epsilon(f)$ error associated to the high-frequency current tones. Regarding the blocking element BlockLF, in the case analysed in this paper, its necessity is not emphasized because the transconductance amplifier used to generate the HF current has a capacitive input impedance able to provide high impedance at 50 Hz.

5. Transient current generating system

5.1. Introduction

The 22NRM06 ADMIT project addresses the characterization of instrument transformers under high-frequency conditions up to 150 kHz in medium-voltage grids. A key challenge is generating large amplitude currents (on the order of kiloamperes) at power frequency with superimposed high-frequency components.

The primary objective of Task A3.1.4 was to develop a transient current generator that can produce a power-frequency current up to 2 kA with superimposed damped high-frequency currents up to 150 kHz. Practically, this meant building a two-source system operating in parallel:

- Main 50 Hz Source: Delivers the fundamental AC current (up to ~2 kA peak) to represent the nominal load current of a power system.
- High-Frequency Source: Delivers a transient damped sinusoidal current, in the frequency range 9 kHz - 150 kHz, with an amplitude up to 500 A_{peak}. This high-frequency current simulates fast oscillatory surges or harmonics superimposed on the fundamental.

Both sources must operate simultaneously and feed into a common load without interfering with each other's performance. This requires a coupling network with filters or impedance separation so that the 50 Hz source and high-frequency source share a test circuit but largely carry currents in their intended frequency bands. The transient current generator is thus expected to produce repeatable combined waveforms, e.g., a 50 Hz 1 kA sine wave with a superimposed 10 kHz damped oscillation of a few hundred amperes, without distortions or damage. Achieving this allows subsequent tasks to evaluate instrument transformer accuracy under these conditions.

5.2. Preliminary tests of two series generators

The initial concept was to implement a circuit in which two current generators were connected in series, with toroidal transformers each supplying current to the same current loop. The secondary windings of these transformers would be arranged such that the first transformer would inject 50 Hz current, while the second would inject high-frequency current. It was already known that the superposition of the fundamental 50 Hz current would lead to core saturation in the high-frequency transformer. To prevent this effect, the approach included the addition of an LC resonant circuit. This resonant branch was designed to be tuned precisely at 50 Hz, thereby shunting the fundamental current around the high-frequency transformer and minimizing its exposure to 50 Hz flux.

However, it was observed that placing the injection transformer in the 50 Hz loop significantly increases the loop's inductance at that frequency, and the 50 Hz transformer is unable to inject current. To give an idea, 10 V on the high-voltage side generate 3.3 A on the low-voltage side. Extrapolating, 400 V on the high-voltage side would produce 130 A on the low-voltage side, which is far below the 2 kA target. Therefore, this initial idea was discarded, and the circuit was redesigned to be a parallel generator. Figure 12 shows the test setup of the preliminary two series generators.

Figure 12. Test setup of the preliminary two series generator.

5.3. Test setup of the two parallel generators

The transient current generator was implemented as two current sources wired in parallel into the same test loop, with appropriate filtering elements.

The 50 Hz source consisted of a high-power AC supply capable of several kiloamperes. In practice, a variable transformer feeding multiple step-down current transformers, e.g. three TORIVAC 10 kVA units in parallel, to generate the 2 kA_{rms} at 50 Hz in the test circuit. These transformers were injecting the current to the 50 Hz loop through several meters of braided copper conductor. This loop also carried a percentage of the HF current, which depends on the inductance ratio between the combined loop inductance and the 50 Hz loop inductance.

The high-frequency source was realized as a resonant RLC discharge circuit triggered by a high-speed switch. It comprised a capacitor bank charged to a specified voltage and then rapidly switched to induce a damped sinusoidal current through the HF injection transformer into the test loop. By adjusting the capacitance and inductance, different oscillation frequencies were achieved. This loop carried the high-frequency transient current and a small portion of the 50 Hz current, which also depended on the impedance ratio at 50 Hz between the combined loop impedance and the HF loop impedance. It is composed of the following components:

- **Capacitor Bank:** Selected to tune the oscillation frequency in combination with the circuit inductance. Various capacitance values, from 0.3 μF up to a 75 μF , were tried to target specific frequencies, e.g. using 0.3 μF for ~ 150 kHz, 75 μF for ~ 9 kHz.
- **Inductances:** Only the inductances inherent to the current loop formed the resonant inductive element. These inductances were calculated to be ~ 4 μH .
- **High Frequency Injection Transformer.** The output of the resonant circuit was coupled to the HF current loop through a high frequency ferrite core transformer. The ratio of the transformer can be selected to be 1:1 or 2:1.
- **Switching Device:** A high-voltage MOSFET transistor was used to switch and connect the charged capacitor to the inductive circuit, discharging the capacitor into the resonant loop. The MOSFET provided controlled triggering of the transient and was tasked to withstand the peak current, tens to hundreds of amperes, during the discharge. The gate of the MOSFET was activated via a fiber optic

trigger. The trigger pulses were generated using a function generator, allowing the triggering of the MOSFET to be synchronized with the zero-crossing or another selectable phase point of the 50 Hz voltage if necessary.

- A coupling network was devised to enable both sources to feed the load without affecting the other transient source. Although a small portion of the 50 Hz current was flowing through the HF loop, some units of amperes were sufficient to saturate the HF injection transformer. Because of this, initially, an explicit compensation branch composed of a series resonant LC filter tuned to 50 Hz was added in parallel with the HF injection transformer to greatly reduce 50 Hz current flow through the HF source. However, this idea was later discarded, as it needed a fine tuning of the LC components. Instead, a 50 Hz capacitive current was applied to a third winding of the HF injection transformer to generate a counteracting 50 Hz flux against the inductive current from the test circuit.

The combined output was injected into a test circuit that mimics the conditions of a current transformer under calibration: a copper sheet of around 1 meter. Figure 13 shows the conceptual schematic of the two parallel generators.

Figure 13. Conceptual schematic of the two parallel generators.

5.4. Test procedure

5.5. Theoretical LC Circuit Calculation

The first step was calculating the theoretical values of capacitance needed, given a chosen inductance, to achieve the target transient frequencies. The inductance was calculated as $L \approx 4 \mu\text{H}$, representative of the high-frequency injection transformer's leakage inductance and the overall circuit wiring. The targeted resonant frequencies were 9 kHz, 15 kHz, 30 kHz, 50 kHz and 150 kHz.

The theoretical sizing provided a starting point for capacitors selection and charging voltages, so that the semiconductor switching device could be selected. Table 2 shows the results of these calculations.

Table 2. Theoretical calculations of the required capacitance values and charging voltage.

I_p (A)	500	500	500	500	500
f (kHz)	9.0	15.0	30.0	50.0	150.0
T/2 (μs)	55.6	33.3	16.7	10.0	3.3
L (μH)	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
C (μF)	78.2	28.1	7.0	2.533	0.281
U_c (V)	113.1	188.5	377.0	628.3	1885.0

5.6. Test circuit characterization.

As specified in previous paragraphs, the 50 Hz current is injected through its own low-inductance path (e.g. a short, thick braid), and the HF transient is injected via the HFCT into the same conductive plate, but not in series with the entire 50 Hz circuit. This created two parallel paths on the plate: one for 50 Hz, one for HF, that meet at common connection points. In this configuration, some fractions of the HF transient current can still circulate through the 50 Hz source and vice versa depending on impedance. This ratio was characterized by using a flat copper plate of 25 cm and 100 cm as the point of coupling between loops. Figure 14 shows the view of the test circuit.

Figure 14. View of the two parallel generators.

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| 1. 50 Hz Transformer and current loop. | 4. Combined output of the current loops. |
| 2. High Frequency Injection Transformer. | 5. Reference current probe. |
| 3. LC resonant circuit to tune the current transients. | 6. Capacitor to compensate the 50 Hz flux flowing into the High Frequency Injection Transformer. |

For this purpose, high-frequency current was measured in both the central HF loop and in the 50 Hz loop using current probes, and similarly the distribution of 50 Hz current between the intended path and any induced into the HF loop was measured. Table 3 and

Table 4 show the current distribution characterization through the different current loops for both the 50 Hz and the HF current injections for the 100 cm bus bar.

Table 3. 50 Hz current measurements through the various current loops.

I_{LV} (A) EUT loop	I_{LV} (A) HF loop	50 Hz Ratio HF/EUT (%)
31.2	1.28E-01	0.41%
64	2.48E-01	0.39%
130	4.96E-01	0.38%
328	1.14E+00	0.35%
2015.4	8.3	0.41%

Table 4. HF current measurements through the various current loops.

f (kHz)	C (nF)	I _{BT} (A) EUT	I _{BT} (A) 50Hz	I _{BT} (A) HF	HF Ratio EUT/HF (%)
90	225	11.6	2.6	18.4	81.92%
		22.6	4.8	31.2	82.48%
		45.6	9.8	59.2	82.37%

The tests showed that over 99.6% of the 50 Hz current remained in the main loop, with only 0.4% coupling into the HF branch. This means that at a current level of 2000 A, 8 A would flow through the HF loop. This issue is addressed in the following paragraphs to avoid core saturation of the HF Injection Transformer. Regarding the HF current injection, it was noted that roughly 80% of the transient current stayed in the “HF loop” portion (the plate and local return), while ~20% flow through the 50 Hz source loop. The HF current transients do not cause any harm to the iron core transformer, but it means that the HF current loop will have to inject an extra 20% of current transient to achieve the objective current.

5.7. Combined 50 Hz and Transient Operation

In the final tests, the transient generator and the 50 Hz high-current source were operated together in the configuration validated earlier. Specifically, a 50 Hz current of 2000 A was established through the main loop, and then transient pulses at various frequencies, 9 kHz, 15 kHz, 25 kHz, 55 kHz, 120 kHz and 160 kHz were injected at different angles of the 50 Hz current: 0°, 60°, 75° and 90°.

The 50 Hz compensation loop was first introduced in this test. Three 112 µF capacitors connected in series were included in the 50 Hz compensation loop, which was energized at the same voltage as the 50 Hz injection transformer.

When a transient was injected at the 50 Hz current zero-crossing, the transient behaved almost identically to the case with no 50 Hz present. The high-frequency oscillation had its full amplitude and frequency content, and the output ratio of the injection transformer was OK. However, when the transient was injected at 90°, the output ratio of the HF injection transformer was clipped, suggesting that the transformer was approaching the magnetic saturation knee. This issue would be solved tuning better the current through the compensation loop. Table 5 shows the results of the tests. Figure 15 shows an example of the combined 50 Hz and the transient current recorded by the oscilloscope.

Table 5. HF current measurements through the various current loops.

Capacitor voltage charge (V)	Capacitance (µF)	Frequency (kHz)	Angle (°)	I _{BT} (A) HF	I _{BT} (A) EUT
191	75	9.25	0	651	553.35
			60	647	549.95
			75	619	526.15
			90	543	461.55
254	30	15	0	617	524.45
			60	613	521.05
			75	605	514.25
			90	549	466.65
452	10	25	0	645	548.25
			60	645	548.25

			75	623	529.55
			90	569	483.65
960	2	55	0	637.0	541.45
			60	634	538.9
			75	615	522.75
			90	559	475.15
1564	0.5	120	0	621	527.85
			60	621	527.85
			75	617	524.45
			90	586	498.1
1575	0.325	161	0	503	427.55
			60	503	427.55
			75	502	426.7
			90	495	420.75

Figure 15. Example of a 50 Hz current signal and a superimposed transient current.

6. Conclusions

This guide has presented six guides on the characterization of instrument current transformers, four solutions guiding on continuous wave approach and two on transients superimposed on 50 Hz line frequency.

Four continuous generation systems give guidance on how to combine a 50 Hz fundamental component with harmonics to 1 kHz up to a total of 2 kA, and continuous high-frequency supraharmonics components 9 – 150 kHz up to 100 A rms for characterization of window type CTs. The 50 Hz fundamental + harmonics components and the high-frequency supraharmonics components 9 kHz - 150 kHz are generated in parallel, and carried through two separate conductors through a window type CT.

Four different choices of current sources for supraharmonics generation have been described, Clarke-Hess 8200 (100 A up to 20 kHz, 20 A up to 150 kHz), Hero-Power DCU 2250-10 FM 1295 by Rohrer Mess- & Systemtechnik (20 A up to 100 kHz and 14 A up to 150 kHz) and Guildline 7620 (20 A up to 100 kHz and 2 A up to 1 MHz)

Four alternatives of measurement systems for characterization of a CT have been described: an NI PXIe-6396 8-ch simultaneously sampling digitizer (1.5 MHz bandwidth, 18 bits), a Yokogawa WT5000 broadband power analyser (1 MHz bandwidth), an Applicos WFD20 2-ch digitizer (2 MHz bandwidth, 20 bits) and Fluke A40B a

Fluke 8588 A multimeter used in digitizer mode with a sampling frequency of 2 MHz. Spectral leakage when using FFT analysis of the signals was addressed.

The fifth guide describes challenges how to generate currents with line frequency and a transient oscillation at high frequency using current sources working in series. The conclusion is that it is not feasible owing to the superposition of the fundamental 50 Hz current would lead to core saturation in the high-frequency transformer. Also, it was observed that placing the injection transformer in the 50 Hz loop significantly increases the loop's inductance at that frequency, and the 50 Hz transformer is unable to inject current.

The sixth guide presents a successful transient current generator which can produce a power-frequency current up to 2 kA with superimposed damped high-frequency currents up to 150 kHz with a two-source system operating in parallel. A main 50 Hz source is used to deliver a fundamental AC current (up to ~2 kA peak) to represent the nominal load current of a power system. A High-Frequency source injects a transient damped sinusoidal current, in the frequency range 9 kHz - 150 kHz, with an amplitude up to 500 A peak. This high-frequency current simulates fast oscillatory surges or harmonics superimposed on the fundamental.

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